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Research

Analyses of the Hybrid bus Passenger's Satisfaction of Lanzhou, China

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Abstract: *The paper examines the service indicators of the newly implemented hybrid bus in Lanzhou city, China, which has not been rigorously studied yet. The bus transport in the city is the only way of mass transportation, which was considered as one of the most polluted cities in the world. It was a big challenge for the policymakers to develop a better transportation system by not hindering the environment. A newer transportation facility always needs to be analyzed if the passengers are accepting this well. Comprehensive exploratory factor analysis has been used to identify the vital service indicators which are finally packed into key factors by the confirmatory factor analysis and regression analysis. Our study suggests that the mass level people care more about their riding experiences than environmental concerns. Transport policymakers can use this information while implementing the new mode of buses.*

Keywords: *Environmental Policy, Transportation Policy, Hybrid Bus, Passenger's Perception. JEL Classification: R41*

Introduction

In the northwestern part of China, Lanzhou is the largest and most important city of Gansu province with a population of more than 3.7 million and with an area of 13100 square kilometers. Lanzhou city is that it was considered as one of the most polluted cities in the world in some studies; the recent steps taken by the local government to face these problems are praiseworthy, transportation sector development is one of them. Mountains surround the city, and as a result, the air cannot pass to other places and stuck in one place, which makes it have the worst quality air among all other Chinese cities. There were some factories where some of them were petroleum based, which are known for polluting the air. During the last decade, it is shifting the factories to some other places. Following the reformation steps, it has introduced the hybrid bus for the transportation purpose, replacing traditional diesel or gas engine mechanism. Another typical way of public transport is the city metro, which is under construction in the city; so, people use the bus as the only way of mass public transportation. This hybrid bus runs from two source or powers, electricity and LNG. The premier objective of the study is to identify the attitudes or perception of the passengers towards the newly introduced hybrid bus of the Lanzhou city of China in the context of satisfaction or comfort

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matter. There are some pure electric buses as well, but for this study, only hybrid buses were selected to find out how they are accepting the hybrid buses.

There are some researches already been done about the passenger satisfaction of public transport in different regions. Redman and others (2013) and Grönroos (1984) gave opinions about how to analyze the satisfaction; the authors have suggested about the comparison of the perception of service along with customer perception. Newly arrived electric or alternative fuel like hydrogen driven engine also got attention among researchers while conducting this research. However, studies about this hybrid vehicle which uses both electric and gas power are yet to be done. Lanzhou is treated as a sensitive place in China because of previous records of its environmental pollution. Steps taken in Lanzhou city can be examples towards other highly polluted cities around the world. Besides, other countries are also buying these kinds of public transport vehicles from China. So, along with the technical issues regarding the bus, public perception of the passengers should be considered to ensure popularity and mass acceptance. There were few studies about the acceptance of hydrogen engine among passengers and were found that people got a negative image of the fuel as they still consider this as risky. As it concerns with thousands of people, the authority to make sure they know precisely what their stakeholders are thinking about the vehicle and improve accordingly. McDowall and Eames (2006) outlined some obstacles to overcome the challenges of hydrogen fuel vehicle, "Overcoming negative public perceptions" is one of them. As the new hybrid bus is also using different fuel mechanism than the traditional bus, it can be considered that this too can be applied to this case. To get positive public perceptions, first, there should be explorations accordingly. The purpose of this research is to identify the satisfaction of passengers with the newly implemented hybrid bus. After getting the responses about the service quality, there should be an improvement which can pull them to use bus services more which is also an excellent solution for urban dwellers who cannot afford the private car and taxi (Currie and Wallis, 2008; Andeeleb and others, 2017). To promote the use of public transport, it is also an essential aspect that when passengers are satisfied with the service, they will recommend it to others (van Lierop and El-Geneidy, 2016). On the other hand, it would be treated as a constraint if there is any passenger dissatisfaction to promote using public transport (Friman, Edvardsson and Gärling, 2001).

The city area is not so big, and it is not possible to ensure a lot of private vehicles on the roads for transportation. There is no alternative way to face the challenge of increasing demand for transport facilities here without improving services like bus or metro. As there was some previously established research work done by some researches, this current work will also follow the preceding paths. The satisfaction level of passengers is defined as the service they are getting compared to what were they expecting earlier (Morfoulaki, Tyrinopoulos and Aifadopoulou, 2010) where Oliver (1997) described it as the customer fulfilment. Budiono (2009) described it as "fulfilment of a need, demand, claim, desires, etc." Most of the previous papers have mentioned issues like speed, comfortability, bus frequency, bus waiting time, cleanliness etc. as the critical factors of satisfaction of bus service. Identifying the level of satisfaction, there would be analyses based on some key issues which would be treated as independent variables. This study wants to know the satisfaction, especially about the hybrid bus, not the whole bus transport system. After introducing hybrid bus in the city, there are no visible infrastructural changes of bus stops or roads only for the

hybrid bus, which means these new buses are using the same infrastructure like before, just only the bus and the engine got changed. So, there would be an elimination of those common issues or variables which are same for both hybrid and other traditional bus services (e.g., bus stop facilities, bus frequency, driver's behaviour towards passengers). There are some standard approaches to measure this service satisfaction (e.g., SERVQUAL or SERVPERF) (McAlexander and others, 1994), but some researchers used original measurements too. The overall satisfaction is tried to discovered by following 12 variables in this paper: comfortability, sitting arrangement, speed, braking, noise efficient, temperature, smell, crowd, travel time, harmfulness, gas emission, pollution reduction (Chou, Lu and Chen, 2014; Das and others, 2013; Lai and Chen, 2011; Dell'Olio, Ibeas and Cecin, 2011; Hydén, 2008; Eboli and Mazzulla, 2007; Pucher and others, 2007; Krizek and El-Geneidy, 2007; Dabholkar and others, 2000; Stuart, Mednick, and Bockman, 2000; Weinstein, 2000).

Study Area

The research work selected passengers from Lanzhou city for the survey. In Lanzhou, around 2568 busses are providing the transportation service every day through 121 routes. About 800 passengers travel by each bus, and that makes approximately 2 million people of Lanzhou are using public bus service. Hybrid bus service has been started since 2010 in the city. As Chinese websites don't have enough information about how many busses exactly are there running by the hybrid technology and no personnel also shared that exact information with the researchers, there is estimation from some news sites that in 2016, there were around 280 hybrid buses which were travelling in 10 routes. There is also an estimation that there were about 1000 hybrid busses installed before 2018 and total 1500 bus during 2018. Usually the bus use YC6J210N-52 engine which consumes 28-33m³ Compressed Natural Gas (CNG) and Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) to run per 100 km. The bus got the smart technology of consuming fuel when the bus speed is below 20/km/h, it uses electricity, and when the speed goes beyond that, it consumes CNG as the fuel.

Methodology

This section would describe the service indicators, the dataset itself used in our further analysis part along with the synopsis of statistical procedures used in our research.

Service indicators

The local government of Lanzhou introduced the hybrid bus in 2010 and so far, there was no prior research done in English in authors' knowledge, which contains the public satisfaction of this bus in Lanzhou. Following the previous studies on different public satisfaction analysis on traditional public transport and different fuel engine public transport, passengers were asked the questionnaires to passengers on board. We intended to ask questions about their satisfaction based on 13 variables which are followed by previous works of literature. The questions regarding those variables were as close-ended questions where there were five possible answers from highly disagree to agree. Selection of the words was chosen carefully to ensure there would be no ambiguity. The questionnaire was developed into the Chinese language as it would be easier for the locals to understand. Table 1 in the analysis part shows the service indicators along with the overviews of collected data.

Source of Data

As there was no secondary source of data in English about the satisfaction level of the hybrid bus among passengers in Lanzhou, there was a need to collect those data from the primary

source. Passengers were briefed about the research purpose first and ensured the anonymity of their details. For about three weeks, the data were collected through the questionnaire from many places all over the Lanzhou city where the data collection team gave the questionnaire to the passengers of the Hybrid bus. In the initial stage, the passengers were asked about if they regular passengers of the Hybrid bus and do they voluntarily agreed to take part in the research. Only regular passengers were asked the questions. The data collection time was from March 22, 2018, to April 11, 2018. The data used here is purely raw data collected from the passengers which are not related to any other resource and without any influence from the government or any other source. The gender, age and occupation-related information are given below to get an indication of the respondents of this study:

Table:1. Summary of respondents' profile (n=716)

Variable		Percent
Gender	Male	47.25%
	Female	52.75%
Age (years old)	16-24	14.90%
	25-34	21.57%
	35-50	25.83%
	50+	37.7%
Employment status	Employed	53.86%
	Taking care of family	7.81%
	Part-time jobs	13.57%
	Unemployed or seeking jobs	7.34%
	Student	17.42%

Data preparation

Total 900 questionnaire forms were distributed among the passengers, and there were some 836 responds collected. Some responses were discarded as those were not filled entirely, only the completely filled responds, and those who are over 16 years old were counted later where the final number of respondents is 716. After collecting data on the paper-based questionnaire, the team builds a workbook sheet with the responses. The workbook was again checked by another group with the questionnaires to find out possible input errors.

Analysis of the data

A descriptive statistic of the collected data is presented in table 1, where variable names were used to concise the writing. Some descriptions were needed to get an overview of the data which is done by spreadsheet and presented in table 2.

Table:2. Descriptive Statistics of variables

No.	Name of the variable	Description of the variable	Mean	S.D.	Var.
OS	overall_satisfacation	Overall satisfaction of hybrid bus service	3.83	.90	.80
1	comfortable	Hybrid bus is comfortable	3.61	1.05	1.10
2	sitting_arrangement	Sitting arrangement in the bus	3.67	.82	.68
3	acceleration	Swift speed up of the bus/acceleration	3.81	.88	.78
4	smooth_braking	Braking is smooth	3.69	.87	.75
5	noise_efficient	Bus runs in a noise efficient way	4.03	.79	.63
6	temperature	Temperature is controlled for hot and cold weather	3.70	.84	.71
7	no_smell	No smell of fuel inside the bus	3.36	1.03	1.06
8	not_crowded	Arrangement of personal space so that it won't feel crowded	3.31	.93	.86
9	same_travel_time	It takes same travel time with traditional bus	3.38	.88	.77
10	less_harmful	Less harmful for the environment	3.65	.95	.90
11	less_gas_emission	It emits less gas and smokes than other busses while running	4.10	.78	.61
12	reduce_pollution	Hybrid bus is contributing to reducing environment pollution	3.99	.822	.68

(S.D. = Standard Deviation; Var.= Variance)

After that, Exploratory Factor Analysis was also done using STATA where this EFA was based on Principal Component Analysis (PCA) that enables direct oblimin rotation of the components as it allows to build correlation with variables (Field, 2009). Tyrinopoulos and Antoniou (2008), Nwachukwu (2014), Morton, Caulfield and Anable (2016) also used either Factor Analysis or Principal Component Analysis for the same kind of earlier research. As the overall satisfaction depends on some indicators, we have collected responses of some variables; however, EFA allows us to get the smaller number of variables which could describe a significant portion of the dependent variable. There was also Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) test done with it to find out sampling adequacy. Hence, the first phase of the analysis also contains a test of Cronbach's alpha (α) to analyze internal consistency and Bartlett's sphericity test. The second phase of the study conducts a Confirmatory Factor Analysis

(CFA) using AMOS to verify the observed structure which was derived from the earlier EFA, this allows to find out the fit of the observed variables with the new structure (Byrne, 2016). The third phase of the analysis consists of Spearman's correlation analysis of the factors and the indicators of satisfaction to find out the possible signification correlation among those. Finally, in the fourth phase, a regression analysis was conducted using the program of the new factors as independent variables against overall satisfaction as the dependent variable. The properties of the data are not continuous, so the Ordinal Logistic Regression was used here (Morton, Caulfield and Anable, 2016).

Table:3. Frequency and Percentage of the Responses

Name of the variable	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	F(#) *	P(%)*	F(#)	P(%)	F(#)	P(%)	F(#)	P(%)	F(#)	P(%)
comfortable	140	19.55	296	41.34	168	23.46	84	11.73	28	3.91
sitting_arrangement	88	12.28	368	51.40	208	29.05	40	5.59	12	1.68
acceleration	140	19.55	368	51.4	156	21.79	36	5.03	16	2.23
smooth_braking	104	14.53	360	50.28	188	26.26	52	7.26	12	1.68
noise_efficient	200	27.93	368	51.4	128	17.88	12	1.68	8	1.12
temperature	80	11.17	424	59.22	152	21.23	40	5.59	20	2.79
no_smell	72	10.06	292	40.78	224	31.28	80	11.17	48	6.70
not_crowded	56	7.82	268	37.43	256	35.75	116	16.2	20	2.79
same_travel_time	64	8.94	256	35.75	300	41.90	80	11.17	16	2.23
less_harmful	132	18.44	296	41.34	212	29.61	60	8.38	16	2.23
less_gas_emission	208	29.05	408	56.98	76	10.61	12	1.68	12	1.68
reduce_pollution	184	25.70	384	53.63	124	17.32	8	1.12	16	2.23
overall_satisfaction	144	20.11	392	54.75	96	13.41	80	11.17	4	0.56

* F=Frequency

**P=Percentage

Figure:1. Graphical Presentation of Overall Satisfaction

For the analysis of the values mathematically, variable rating responses are given points where Strongly Agree is assigned with 5 points, Agree = 4, Neutral = 3, Disagree = 2 and Strongly Disagree = 1. Variables with mean value equal or more than 3 would indicate satisfaction, and less than 3 says about dissatisfaction. Figure 2 displays the mean distributions.

Figure:2. Mean Distribution of Variables

Results

Exploratory Factor Analysis

The findings of the Exploratory Factor Analysis are given below in table 3. The conducted EFA indicates that there are some factors which can define the overall satisfaction level of the passengers regarding the hybrid bus those can be used instead of all the 12 opinion questions mentioned earlier. The loadings were rotated after EFA, which helps to improve the readability of the data, and the variables were considered with a significant level of 0.40, as suggested by (Hair and others, 1998). The independent variables are connected to three factors where the factors were generated based on Factor Analysis using principal-component factors methods. Before doing the test, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy says the score is 0.855, which is in suitable fit according to previous researchers (Morton, Caulfield Anable, 2016). There was also a Bartlett test of sphericity which shows the p-value is 0.000, which is adequate. After conducting the factor analysis, there was a test conducted to check the Cronbach's alpha measure of internal consistency (α) which also shows an acceptable score for whole model ($\alpha=0.88$) and each of those factors (0.83, 0.83 and 0.73). As suggested by Kaiser (1960), we have picked three factors which got eigenvalue more than 1 after the scree test (Cattell, 1966) which is now shown in this paper and this also follows the statement of Zwick and Velice (1986) where they mentioned about at least three factors with significant loadings.

Factor 1, as we got from the factor analysis, has the eigenvalue of 5.31, which explains 44.26% of all of the explained variance. This first factor consists of variables which are smooth_braking, acceleration, comfortable, sitting_arrangement, noise_efficient and temperature. This paper named the new factor as “comfortability of journey”.

The second factor consists of the variables named reduce_pollution, less_gas_emission, and less_harmful. These variables are related to the protection of the environment, and that is why we can call it "environmental issues." Explaining 10.44% of the total variance, this factor has an eigenvalue of 1.25.

There is another factor which has an eigenvalue of 1.15 that accounts for 9.55% of explained variance. This factor has significant loadings like not_crowded (0.91), same_travel_time (0.89) and no_smell (0.49) and can be labeled as “onboard experience”.

Table:4. Oblimin Rotated factor loadings (pattern matrix) and Unique Variances, Sorted

No.	Variables	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
4	smooth_braking	0.8730*	0.0484	0.0097
3	acceleration	0.8269*	0.0594	0.0440
1	comfortable	0.7896*	0.0760	0.1759
2	sitting_arrangement	0.6468*	0.1571	0.0370
5	noise_efficient	0.5232*	0.2662	0.0191
6	temperature	0.4173*	0.0564	0.3784
12	reduce_pollution	0.0334	0.9318*	0.0613
11	less_gas_emission	0.0361	0.9150*	0.0920
10	less_harmful	0.0770	0.7984*	0.1041
8	not_crowded	-0.0713	-0.0138	0.9119*
9	same_travel_time	0.0072	-0.1089	0.8934*
7	no_smell	0.1242	0.2298	0.4850*

* significant loadings are 0.40 (followed by previous literature)

Confirmatory factor analysis

After the exploratory factor analysis, further evaluation is done through the confirmatory factor analysis using statistical software AMOS. This model building feature analyzed the first model directly derived from the EFA earlier and got the model fit of which is not acceptable following the CFA benchmark ($X^2 = 509.440; df = 51; \text{Root Mean Square Error of Approximation or } RMSEA = 0.112; \text{Confirmatory Factor Index or } CFI = 0.880; \text{Tucker-Lewis Index or } TLI = 0.844 \text{ and Standardized Root Mean Square Residual or } SRMR = 0.060$). However, the modification indices and standardized residuals suggest and improved model fit. Two variables, acceleration, and no_smell are removed from the model which were in the group of latent variables comfortability of journey and onboard experience. Besides, error terms covariances were shown in another modified model between statement number 2 and 3; 2 and 4.

This modified CFA shows improved model fit according to the CFA benchmark ($X^2 = 154.563, df = 30, RMSEA = 0.076, CFI = 0.956, TLI = 0.933 \text{ and } SRMR = 0.035$) which can be stated as an acceptable model fit (Hooper, Coughlan and Mullen, 2008). This better solution is presented in the figure below:

Figure:3. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Correlation analysis

After the factor analysis, there is a Spearman's correlation analysis with the dependent variable was conducted to find out the possible correlation among these findings of the

reduced number of variables. The analysis shows that there is a moderately strong correlation exists among those new variables and overall satisfaction (0.598; 0.425; 0.400). This also implies that the data we have collected can be treated as useful indicators of the passenger satisfaction of the hybrid bus as public transport.

Table:5. Spearman’s Correlation Analysis

Variables	A	B	C	D
comfortability of journey (A)	1.0000			
environmental issues (B)	0.4678**	1.0000		
onboard experience (C)	0.3990**	0.4598**	1.0000	
satisfaction(D)	0.5981**	0.4251**	0.4000**	1.0000

** : p-value < 0.01

Regression analysis

At this part of the analysis, there is regression after the factor analysis to identify the relation of the perceived factors through EFA with the overall satisfaction. The overall satisfaction level is ordinal in its nature, so the regression conducted here is an ordinal logistic regression. This model would provide with insights into the topic. In the part of the dependent variable, overall satisfaction is used as it is ordinal in nature, and the independent variables include the comfortability of journey, environmental issues, and onboard experience. The results are shown below:

Table:6. Regression analysis of Analysis

<i>Variable</i>	β	<i>Std. Err.</i>	<i>Wald</i>	<i>95% Conf. Int.</i>
comfortability of journey	1.399**	0.109	165.493	1.186-1.612
environmental issues	0.249**	0.096	6.751	0.061-0.437
onboard experience	0.429**	0.094	20.741	0.244-0.614

Model Fit

-2LL (intercept)	1712.165
-2LL (final)	1334.654
χ^2 (df = 3)	377.511**
Nagelkerke R^2	0.451

** p-value < 0.01

The above model shows the Nagelkerke pseudo R^2 value as 0.451, which indicates that this model with these three variables can describe 45.1% of the overall satisfaction. The model fit derived from the statistical package suggests that there is some degree of significance of all the variables over the dependent variable. Coefficients or the beta originated from the model suggests the insights of the variables. The largest coefficient, comfortability of journey got the most significant impact (Beta: 1.399) on the measure of overall satisfaction, and this

factor consists of *comfortable, sitting_arrangement, acceleration, smooth_braking, noise_efficient* and *temperature*. The second largest coefficient named as onboard experience (Beta: 0.429) which describes *no_smell, same_travel_time* and *not_crowded*. The smallest coefficient is shown by the third variable environmental issues (Beta: 0.249) consists of *less harmful, less gas emission, and reduce pollution*. For simplicity and less number of variables, this study has intentionally excluded other vital variables like driver and personnel's attitudes, on-time performance, the frequency of bus service, network coverage, stop location, waiting time, waiting conditions, transfer time etc. (Mahmoud and Hine, 2016; Chou, Lu and Chang, 2014; de Oña and others, 2013; Stradling and others, 2007) as we observed that both traditional bus service and the Hybrid bus use the same facilities; however, those factors also describe a significant portion of passenger satisfaction of public transport service.

Discussion

As we know from earlier researches, overcoming negative perceptions are vital for adopting new technology in the transport sector, this study tried to find out the issues that the passengers are considering most. After empirical analysis, we can see the following factors have more significant impacts on their perception.

Comfortability of journey

The most critical component the research found is the comfortability of the journey. Previous studies also support this finding that people care most about whether the bus ride is comfortable enough. Lanzhou bus authority already managed satisfactory hardware arrangements in their public transport where the Hybrid bus is also following the trend. Having the most significant impact on overall satisfaction, there is still a big chance for the authority to improve the satisfaction level to ensure better sitting arrangements, smooth speeding, and braking etc. Lanzhou is a place with mostly cold weather situated in the northwestern part of China, and people expect to keep themselves warm enough inside during their journey. However, during summer or hot days, there should be adequate cooling arrangements. The hybrid bus uses the mechanism of big batteries as the alternative or supporting fuel which occupies some space of seats. Future models of the busses can be set by minimizing this space. Authorities can come forward and monitor the bus comfort from time to time.

Environmental issues

Passengers are concerned about the environmental issues according to the model as mentioned above. Hybrid bus surely is working against the environment pollution by using electricity as the alternative fuel along with additional fuel mechanisms, people of Lanzhou think this is still not enough to reduce adequate pollution. Hybrid buses can be changed into a fully electric bus later or with other alternative fuel like hydrogen engine to meet this issue. Besides, there should be more public awareness of how precisely the newer buses are making a difference in leaving less impact on the environment would clarify to the passengers.

Onboard experience

The last factor, onboard experience also plays a vital role to determine the overall satisfaction count of the hybrid bus in Lanzhou city. There are some issues or complains about smell inside the bus while running which consists of body odor of passengers and the smell from the engines; some passengers complained about feeling like vomiting sometimes due to the bad smell. To face this problem, the air cleaning system should be strengthened. The bus can

be felt more crowded during the rush hours; more buses can be arranged to meet this problem. A right way is to find out the proper ratios of people traveling from different places and busses from less essential or fewer passengers can be shifted to the more important route during rush hours along with allocating more busses. Roads built in Lanzhou is already satisfactory and can be improved more to avoid traffic jam during rush hours. There are already some proper arrangements can be seen; Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) is one of them which can be built all over Lanzhou city.

Passenger Opinion

For further knowing what people are thinking about the hybrid bus beside the questionnaire set by this research, there was an open-ended part where people could write down their opinion, complains or anything else. Though this research was based on what's new on this hybrid bus, some passengers commented about total public bus system which will be mentioned here. Some people suggested that the road infrastructure should be more developed and that is how they can get more advantages from the newly arrived hybrid bus. There are a lot of complaints about motion sickness inside the bus, and passengers feel dizzy. The air conditioning system should be developed to meet this problem. Speed is not stable in comparison to other traditional busses through the starting speed up is fast, bus authorities should monitor this issue. Along with that, acceleration and brakes are expected to be smoother. Drivers are requested to improve their driving skills and not to drive fierce. Regarding the engine power, some are concerned about electricity usage, and they suggested to ensure proper maintenances of the batteries to avoid any risks. Though the noise of the bus while running is not so loud, there are suggestions about putting the volume down of the television or advertising inside the bus.

Conclusions

The study shows that people are mostly satisfied with the existing hybrid bus service in Lanzhou city, although there are some suggestions or more expectations for this bus. Passengers prefer the comfort of the bus service most along with the environmental issues and their experience of the bus journey. The authority of the bus in Lanzhou should monitor these significant issues frequently. Further development of comfort and other issues will be likely to improve the acceptance of this bus among passengers. People are now aware of the environmental effects they are causing with the vehicles; hybrid bus could help them to feel that they can contribute to reducing this problem together. This significant study can be a guideline for the further enhancement of service quality in the transportation of Lanzhou and also any other place where the hybrid bus is to be installed.

The research has used some determinants to study passenger satisfaction, which is usually applicable for the hybrid bus only, and it has intentionally skipped the other general determinants which are for all kinds of busses. The findings can be used in designing and implementing the new hybrid bus in other parts of the world. The study area was limited into a comparatively small city of China, which may not be applicable for the bigger cities. A rigorous future analysis can be done this field, which would count all the other variables as well. Lanzhou was an ideal place to study about the bus in remote locations as it does not have the city metro yet and most of the people use it as the only way for mass transportation. However, there should be more research on the hybrid bus in other bigger cities in China to find out how developing countries are accepting the hybrid technologies for transport service

with or without other alternative mass transit opportunities. There are more researches expected to be done in English with information from China. Additional research should be done from the technological perspective as well to get further insights.

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